

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND MICRO- STRUCTURE OF LAYERED Al-4.5% Cu/10% TiB₂ COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Metal matrix composite (MMC) with composition of Al-4.5wt.%Cu reinforced by 10wt.%TiB₂ particulate has been successfully fabricated using powder metallurgy. Two different types of disk shaped specimens were prepared: (a) layered structure containing ductile Al-4.5wt.%Cu with brittle Al-4.5wt.%Cu/TiB₂ layers, and (b) homogeneous constituent with composition of Al-4.5wt.%Cu/10wt.%TiB₂. The brittle layer consisted of Al-4.5%Cu with fixed amount of TiB₂ reinforcement. Although the weight ratio of Al-4.5%Cu to TiB₂ particulate for the brittle layer varied from 1:1, 2:1, 3:1 to 5:1, the overall composition of the specimen was maintained as Al-4.5wt.%Cu/10wt.%TiB₂. The mechanical properties of the specimens were measured in terms of fracture toughness, K_{IC} . Two types of fracture behaviours have been observed: (a) type-I for layered specimens and (b) type III for homogeneous MMC specimens. The volume fraction of TiB₂ in the brittle layer was found to have a significant effect on the load versus displacement curves even though the fracture toughness of the layered MMC was not enhanced significantly. More ductile behaviour had been observed in the layered MMC than in the homogeneous specimen. Owing to the existence of ductile layers, crack propagation can be resisted. The ductile layer manifests a strong influence on delaying the fracture. It acts as a barrier to resist the propagation of crack and hence increases the fracture toughness of the layered MMC specimens.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs), which provide high modulus, improved wear resistance and strength, have been recognized as having great potential for advanced structural applications [1-3]. The major limitation in the mechanical properties of MMCs is their limited ductility in comparison to their base metals. Cracks normally initiate from reinforcement and voids [3, 4]. Due to the lack of ductility, cracks propagate rapidly with increase in load. As a result, the interactions between reinforcement particles and propagating cracks have recently been of great research interest [5]. In addition, volume fraction of reinforcement and aging condition of the matrix significantly affect the mechanical behaviour of MMCs. In the case of Al-3.5%Cu reinforced with varying volume fractions of SiCp, it was found that the probability of particle fracture increased with increasing volume fraction of reinforcement [6]. To improve the ductility of MMCs, MMCs made from alternating ductile and brittle layers have recently received much

attention because mechanical properties such as toughness can be improved by engineering different layers of ductile and brittle constituents [7-10].

In the present study, layered and homogeneous MMCs with composition of Al-4.5wt.%Cu reinforced by 10wt.%TiB₂ particulate were fabricated using powder metallurgy technique. Microstructure and fracture toughness of the materials were studied and compared.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material and Specimen Preparation

Two different types of disk shaped specimens were prepared: (a) layered structure containing ductile Al-4.5wt.%Cu with brittle Al-4.5wt.%Cu/TiB₂ layers, and (b) homogeneous constituent with composition of Al-4.5wt.%Cu/10wt.%TiB₂. The normal direction of the layers in the layered specimens, being built through three ductile-brittle-ductile alternating layers was parallel to the axis of the disk specimen. The brittle layer consisted of Al-4.5%Cu with fixed amount of TiB₂ reinforcement. Although the weight ratio of Al-4.5%Cu to TiB₂ particulate for the brittle layer varied from 1:1, 2:1, 3:1 to 5:1, denoted here as LS1-1, LS2-1, LS3-1 and LS5-1, the overall composition of the specimen was kept as Al-4.5wt.%Cu/10wt.%TiB₂. The particle sizes of Al, Cu and TiB₂ used in this study were 100 μm, 50 μm and 5 μm respectively. The powder particles were blended for 18 ks and then cold-compacted to a disk of 25 mm diameter and 9 mm thickness. The specimens were heated to 423 K for 3.6 ks and then sintered at 873 K in an atmosphere controlled furnace for 10.8 ks. They were finally solution treated at 790 K for 14.4 ks and peak-aged at 447 K for 68.4 ks.

Mechanical Properties

Fracture toughness of the material in terms of K_{IQ} , the tentative value of K_{IC} , was measured with test procedures in accordance with the ASTM E399-83 standard [11] using an Instron testing machine. The speed of crosshead speed was controlled at 0.5 mm/min. K_Q (MPa.m^{1/2}) was evaluated from the following equation [11]:

$$K_Q = \left(\frac{P_Q}{B\sqrt{W}} \right) f \left(\frac{a}{w} \right) \quad (1)$$

where P_Q is the 5% secant load (kN), B , the specimen thickness (cm), W , specimen width (cm), a , the crack length (cm) and $f(a/w)$, a geometry dependent constant.

Microstructure and Fractography

Microstructures at the cross section of the specimens were studied using optical microscope, while the fracture surfaces after fracture toughness testing were examined on a JEOL JSM-T330A scanning electron microscope (SEM) at an operating voltage of 15 kV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure of Sintered Specimens

The typical interfacial microstructure between ductile and brittle layers of the layered specimens is shown in figure 1 (a). It can be seen that one layer contains TiB₂ reinforcement, while the other one contains only base metal. They were well bonded together with no visible boundary between them. Figures 1 (b) to 1 (f) reveal the microstructure of the layered and the homogeneous specimens. It may be seen that the porosity in the brittle layer with high volume fraction of TiB₂ is higher than those with low volume fraction of TiB₂ because it was difficult to cold-compact

Figure 1. Microstructure of the test specimens: (a) at interface between ductile and brittle layers; (b) LS1-1; (c) LS2-1; (d) LS3-1; (e) LS5-1; and (f) homogeneous specimens.

composite layers with high fraction of reinforcement. LS1-1 specimen which contains the highest volume fraction of TiB_2 in the brittle layer shows the highest volume of porosity while the homogeneous specimen shows the lowest. Because of too high volume fraction of reinforcement in the LS1-1 and LS2-1, large clusters of the reinforcement could be observed. The ductile layers, however, were denser than the brittle layers. The existence of porosity is associated with particle clusters. The density measurements of the normal homogeneous and layered specimens are shown in Table 1.

Mechanical property

The load versus clip-gauge displacement curves in figures 2 (a) to 2 (e) show two types of fracture: (a) type-I for layered specimens and (b) type-III for the homogeneous specimens. The variation of fracture toughness with the difference in the volume fraction of reinforcement in the composite layer (brittle layer) is given in Table 1. From figure 2 and Table 1, it can be seen that the volume fraction of TiB_2 in the brittle layer exerts a significant effect on the load versus displacement curves of the material even though the fracture toughness for the layered MMC was not enhanced significantly. The layered MMC, however, showed more ductile behaviour than the homogeneous specimen. Generally, fracture toughness of the specimen initially showed an increase with the decrease in volume fraction of the reinforcement in the brittle layers, even though the volume fraction of TiB_2 remained the same for all specimens. The toughness, however, decreased with further decrease in volume fraction of the reinforcement.

In principle, improvement in fracture toughness or other mechanical properties is the contributions of ductile and brittle layers. Some experimental results have demonstrated that fracture toughness decreases with the increase in volume fraction of reinforcement, while yield strength and modulus show an increase when volume fraction of reinforcement is increased [2, 12, 13]. The fracture toughness as a function of volume fraction of reinforcement can be expressed by the following equation [14]:

$$K_{Ic} \equiv \left[2\sigma_y E \left(\frac{\pi}{6} \right)^{1/3} D \right]^{1/2} V^{-1/6} \quad (2)$$

where σ_y is the yield stress, E , Young's modulus, D , the particle diameter and V , the volume fraction of particles. Eq. (2) suggests that fracture toughness decreases with the increase in volume fraction of reinforcement if σ_y remains constant. In the present study, fracture toughness of the ductile layer may be assumed identical for all the specimens since there was no change in the composition in the ductile layers. The fracture toughness of the brittle layer, however, changed from specimen to specimen due to the difference in volume fraction of the reinforcement. When the fracture toughness of the brittle layer is increased due to a decrease in the volume fraction of the reinforcement, the contribution to fracture toughness from the ductile layers will consequently be reduced due to the reduction in the thickness of the ductile layers. It was found that the decrease in toughness was most significant from zero to 10% reinforcement, with only a slight decrease for higher reinforcement [15]. It is expected that there is an optimum balance between the contribution to fracture toughness from the ductile layers and that from brittle layers.

Besides the influence of volume fraction of reinforcement on fracture toughness, as observed from microscopy, the high volume fraction of reinforcement could lead to a decrease in density and an increase in brittleness. It is noted from Table 1 that the value of K_Q of the homogeneous specimen is close to those of the layered ones. It is believed that the high value of K_Q for the homogeneous specimen is due mainly to its high density. Hence, if the density can be

Table 1. Variation in K_Q , K_{max} and density

Specimen No.	Measured density/theoretic density (%)	K_Q (MPa m ^{-1/2})	K_{max}^* (MPa m ^{-1/2})
LS 1-1	89.4	17.7	24.8
LS 2-1	89.8	18.7	22.7
LS 3-1	89.9	17.8	22.3
LS 5-1	90.1	17.9	18.3
NM	91.2	17.7	17.7

* K_{max} is calculated using the maximum value of load P_{max}

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Fig.2. Load versus clip-gage displacement curves of normal and layered MMC specimens.

increased, both the yield stress and the fracture toughness would be expected to increase. It is also expected that the fracture toughness of the layered specimens be increased if the thickness of the specimens is increased.

Morphologies of Fracture Surfaces

The morphologies of the fractured surfaces are given in figures 3 (a) to (g). It is noted from microstructural observation that cracks normally were initiated from the brittle layer because of the nature of the brittle constituent. A majority of the cracks in the brittle layers was found to be located near the TiB_2 particles. Propagation of cracks stopped once the cracks reached the interface between brittle and ductile layers. The latter appears to act as barrier to resist crack propagation. This phenomenon is believed to be the reason for the increase in fracture toughness for the layered MMC in comparison to the homogeneous specimen. Very ductile fracture surface in the ductile layers in terms of dimples was observed (figure 3 (f)).

Although LS1-1 specimen showed a very tough behaviour, delamination in the brittle zone was found near the interface between the ductile and the brittle layers as indicated by the arrows in figure 3 (a). The formation of delamination is believed to be the result of the formation of three dimensional stresses during the fracture test. Because toughness of the reinforced layers was lower than that without the reinforcement, fracture initially started from the brittle layers while the ductile layers were still under plastic deformation. Gradual necking in the ductile layers was observed for all layered specimens during fracture test. Because of the occurrence of necking, three dimensional stresses were generated. When the stress normal to the disk specimens reached the ultimate tensile strength of the brittle layer, cracks were initiated. There are two possibilities for the initiation of delamination. Delamination between two different layers could be initiated before crack started in the brittle layers. It could also be initiated after the fracture of the brittle layers. In general, toughness of the brittle layers was very low. The normal stress between different layers depends on the amount of necking. It is believed that there was no significant necking to generate enough normal stresses before the formation of crack. Hence, delamination most likely started after the fracture crack of the brittle layers.

Delamination between two different layers was also observed in the LS2-1 specimen indicating the occurrence of poor bonding. When the thickness of the brittle layer was increased as in LS3-1 and LS5-1 specimens, no delamination was observed. Another evidence observed was that if the volume fraction of reinforcement was too high, a large number of TiB_2 particles aggregated together to form porous clusters with base metal in between as show in figures 3 (b) and 3 (c). Because the sintering temperature was far below the diffusion temperature of TiB_2 , there was no diffusion bonding between these particles. This situation has been improved by decreasing volume fraction of the reinforcement as shown in figures 3 (d), 3 (e) and 3 (g) from which it can be seen that the TiB_2 particles are better distributed in the base metal. Three types of fracture modes are generally noticeable: (i) debonding between TiB_2 and base metal as shown in figures 3 (e) and 3 (g); (ii) formation of voids as in figure 3 (e); and (iii) dimple fracture as in figures 3 (d) to 3 (f). The type of the fracture mode depended on the volume fraction of the reinforcement. When the volume fraction of TiB_2 is high, inter-particle fracture dominated. With low fraction of TiB_2 , voids in the ductile areas could be observed. Debonding between matrix and the reinforcement could always be observed.

According to microstructural and morphological observations and the value of fracture toughness determined, it can be seen that the best combination of ductile and brittle layer is LS3-1 where the weight ratio of Al-4.5%Cu to TiB_2 is 3:1.

Figure 3. Morphologies of fracture surfaces: (a) interfacial delamination between two different layers; (b) LS1-1; (c) LS2-1; (d) LS3-1; (e) LS5-1; (f) ductile layer; (g) homogeneous specimens

CONCLUSIONS

- (a) Layered MMC specimens were successfully prepared using powder metallurgy. The enhancement of fracture toughness of layered MMC specimens was achieved. Fracture tests showed that layered specimens exhibited type-I load versus displacement curves while the normal homogeneous specimen showed a type-III load versus displacement curve.
- (b) Delamination in LS1-1 and LS2-1 specimens have been observed in the brittle zone near the interface between the brittle and the ductile layers. It is believed that the delaminations were caused by the formation of necking in the ductile layer after the fracture of the brittle layers.
- (c) The ductile layer manifested a strong influence on delaying the fracture. It acted as a barrier to resist the propagation of crack and hence increased the fracture toughness of the layered MMC specimens.
- (d) According to microstructural observation and the fracture toughness measured, the best combination of ductile and brittle layer is LS3-1.

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